

CONSULTATION SUPPORT PLATFORM

Online tools supporting the consultation process

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Summary

A core activity of the EcoAdvance project programme is consultation. To support the consultation process a system for online registration and implementation of surveys was developed. CDE activities encouraged people to register and participate in the surveys, including recommendations for potential projects and consultees to follow up on.

Following the initial project work period, the approach was refined and simplified to encourage wider participation through a revised programme of engagement.

Deliverable D2-5 comprises delivery of the online consultation platform designed to facilitate the consultation process through registration of consultees and implementation of surveys. This report provides an overview of the team approach taken to develop the platform, the surveys and how it works. The report has also been extended to include details of changes made to both survey content and approach for the 2nd project period, based upon recommendations arising from a review of survey progress made during period 1.

1 Objectives & Approach

1.1 Objectives

A core activity of the EcoAdvance project programme is consultation - see Figure 1 project workflow diagram. Most of the actions under work package 2 (WP2 – pink shading) relate to review and establishing contacts with people and projects, whereas the work under work package 3 (WP3 – orange shading) relates to consultation and analysis of the consultee responses.

Figure 1 EcoAdvance workflow diagram

The earlier WP2 project deliverables combine to identify people and projects appropriate for subsequent consultation. These deliverables comprised:

- D2.1 Preliminary Review of Information on Factors Affecting the Success of Restoration Projects
- D2.2 Freshwater Ecosystem Restoration: A bibliographic review
- D2.3 Potential showcasing success people and projects
- D2.4 Factors Driving Success

with the workflow as shown in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2 Initial review workflow process

To support the subsequent consultation process it was considered that implementing a system of online registration and surveys would be the most efficient way to both encourage participation and to collect, manage and analyse the survey data.

This report details the development and content of the online tools (i.e. Deliverable D2.5) intended to support the consultation process.

1.2 Approach

With the expectation of encouraging hundreds of responses, the approach taken was to develop a bespoke system for the project that combined online registration with the implementation of surveys. To ensure that we could develop exactly what was wanted by / for the project, this system of web content underpinned by a database was coded directly.

This approach has been used successfully on another European project where widespread consultation was sought, with multiple stages of feedback requested.

This approach also allowed us to:

- Test and adapt the approach according to perceived usability and complexity.
- Ensure that ethical procedures and GDPR rules could be followed regarding data collection, use and security.
- Easily track registrations and participation

The consultation process comprised the following steps:

1. People (contacts identified from the earlier WP2 review activities) would be encouraged to register online and participate in the survey
2. When someone registered, their request details were sent to a team member for review and approval, prior to confirmation and access to project surveys. This step helped avoid automated bots registering and disrupting the system.
3. When consultees completed a survey, a team member was notified
4. All registration and survey data was stored online, accessible by the administrator. This helped team compliance with GDPR regulations. Survey data could be exported for analysis when required.

2 Implementation

The system was implemented in 2 stages:

- Stage 1: Registration and a simple survey
- Stage 2: Main Survey, Interview & Showcase Materials

Stage 1 was completed within the first few months of the project so that we could steer people towards the project website from social media posts promoting the EcoAdvance work. Stage 2 was developed later in 2023.

The consultation platform could be accessed from the EcoAdvance website homepage (www.ecoadvance.eu) – see Figure 3. The main navigation to ‘Consultation’ provided an explanation of the consultation goals along with details of how the survey information would be used (Figure 4). From here you could register to participate in the survey process and access the ‘Consultation Platform’ home page (Figure 5).

Figure 3 EcoAdvance website home page

Figure 4 EcoAdvance consultation introduction

Figure 5 EcoAdvance consultation platform navigation page

This format of the Consultation Platform home page allowed you to select which level of survey you would like to undertake and, if you have followed up with a personal interview and the creation of showcasing material, to also access and view those materials.

The format and content of these survey pages can be found in the Appendices as follows:

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|----------------|
| (1) Simple Survey | See Appendix A |
| (2) Main Survey – Personal Experience | See Appendix B |
| (3) Main Survey – Project Experience | See Appendix C |
| (4) Interview & Showcase Materials | See Appendix D |

2.1 Approach to survey development

Development of the surveys was undertaken primarily by the EcoAdvance partner HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, who are also leading actions under WP3 and hence the analysis of survey responses. The survey was also reviewed, tested and refined by the whole EcoAdvance team to help ensure suitability across European Member States.

The content of the survey was developed based upon initial findings from the review work and expectations as to likely topics that would ultimately contribute to development of the Prone2Success checklist. Ultimately, development of the Prone2Success Checklist would build upon feedback arising from the surveys and subsequent consultation, hence development of the surveys and checklist is an iterative process.

The format of the surveys was developed to try and make them as flexible for consultees as possible. The style of questions and the nature of response options was refined to try and minimize the effort needed by the consultees. For example, selection of response options to a question was chosen over a free format response wherever possible to make it easier and quicker to complete.

The number of questions and length of survey was also debated in depth and refined several times to try and ensure that valuable data is collected whilst requiring the minimum effort by the consultee. There is a fine balance to be made in developing this process.

2.2 Different surveys

Ultimately, 3 different surveys were created. These comprised:

- 1 Quick survey
- 2 Main survey (Personal Experience)
- 3 Main survey (Project Experience)

The quick survey was completed as part of the initial registration process, whereas the 'Main Surveys' required the consultee to return (following registration approval) and complete a more detailed survey.

Screen shots showing details of the Quick Survey can be found in **Appendix A**.

Screen shots showing details of the Main Survey (Personal Experience) can be found in **Appendix B**.

Screen shots showing details of the Main Survey (Project Experience) can be found in **Appendix C**.

It was considered important to differentiate between personal and project experience since the focus for EcoAdvance is to highlight factors that make projects prone to success through consultation and analysis of personal experience - talking to the people who had undertaken the work and succeeded in addressing the challenges of restoration work. We also included a survey relating to project experience because there is a tendency for people to talk about and refer to work on specific projects when recounting their experiences.

The first part of the Main Survey related to expert opinion on Freshwater Ecosystem Restoration issues, based on general knowledge and work experience.

The second part of the Main Survey asked for specific project experiences, good practices, policy recommendations and to define key factors which help to improve the chances of project success and hence contribute to the Prone2Success Checklist.

2.3 Data export and analysis

All of the survey data submitted is stored online in a secure database, and can be exported for analysis as required by the team. By undertaking the surveys online and storing the data online we help ensure consistency between partners and compliance with ethical procedures and GDPR regulations.

The data export allows partners to review responses categorised by country and to follow up with registrants as potential consultees and sources for showcase generation.

3 Survey Response and Next Steps

3.1 Survey Response

The survey was promoted via social media posts, team participation in restoration events and team consultation outreach activities (i.e. individual emails, messages and calls to contacts identified in the initial review activities). At the time of Period 1 review (Spring 2024) the number of consultees who had registered was ~80 people. These included responses from Austria (2), Belgium (2), Croatia (1), Cyprus (2), Czech Republic (10), Denmark (1), Estonia (1), France (1), Germany (3), Greece (1), Hungary (13), Ireland (3), Israel (6), Italy (3), Latvia (1), Lithuania (1), Malta (5), Netherland (4), Norway (1), Romania (5), Serbia (2), Slovakia (3), Slovenia (1), Spain (1), Sweden (1), Switzerland (2), UK (3), USA (2).

Whilst consultees registered and participated in the initial quick survey, participation in the main surveys was only undertaken by 7 people. The rate of follow through from social media to quick survey and on to the main surveys was poor.

However, follow up with each of the individual registrants was not possible prior to the 1st period project review and subsequent reviewer recommendations to restructure the approach.

During the PR1 review it was recommended that the team consider simplifying and streamlining the consultation process by:

- Making it simpler and clearer as to how data would be used
- Making access to the survey simpler and quicker – primarily by not requesting and then confirming consultee registration prior to the consultee then needing to return at a later point for the main survey)
- Simplifying the surveys, such that consultees could complete more quickly

3.2 Next Steps

3.2.1 Simplified survey

Following the PR1 feedback it was concluded that we would restructure the entire survey process, creating a single, shorter and simpler survey by:

- (i) Removing the need to register online – instead making the survey anonymous but with the option to provide contact details at the end of the survey (to receive copies of results, follow up consultation etc.).
- (ii) Using Google Docs for survey creation instead of coding the survey directly, allowing for a quicker turnaround of survey creation and easier creation of different language versions.
- (iii) Ensuring simpler and clearer webpage access to the survey

In simplifying and creating a new single survey, consideration was again given to which topics were most likely to feature in the consultation feedback and eventual Prone2Success checklist. We separated questions into different topics to understand the roles of community engagement, tools and guidance, ecosystem services, and regulations & policies in the success of projects. A copy of the new survey questions can be found in Appendix E.

Prior to widespread promotion of the survey, the content and structure will initially be reviewed by members of the EC Dalia project for external feedback on focus and format. Following this, it is envisaged that the survey will be promoted online from July 2024 and responses reviewed after an initial couple of months.

3.2.2 Updated engagement plan

An updated engagement plan has also been developed in parallel to the updated survey. In comparison to period 1, a greater focus has been placed on personal consultation with other projects and restoration networks in order to garner responses from groups of established practitioners and experts. For example, consultation with the WG-A ECOSTAT Group and with Danube initiatives (such as the Dalia Project) along with the ECRR (European Centre for River Restoration). At the same time, promotion via the EcoAdvance social media sites will be recommenced. Full details of this strategy can be found in the updated CDE plan.

4 Conclusions

During Period 1 of the project the initial work programme plan of developing a consultation platform to help promote and manage the EcoAdvance survey and consultation process was created and used. An initial response was received from ~80 consultees.

Building on the Period 1 review feedback, the consultation approach was modified in the initial months of Period 2. The survey structure was simplified and reduced whilst accessibility was improved by removing the need to register personal details prior to participation. In addition, the survey process was simplified by removing the bespoke consultation platform and moving to the use of the survey templates available within Google Docs.

External feedback on the format and content of the survey was sought from a partner EC project (Dalia), and promotion to encourage wider consultation will start in July 2024.

Appendices

Appendix A: Quick Survey

Quick Survey

Quick Survey (* = required)

Have you been directly involved in a freshwater ecosystem restoration project (as a planner, engineer, community stakeholder, decision-maker, activist, etc.) in the last 20 years? *

Yes

In your experience (covering all projects undertaken), what are the top 3 factors that contribute most to a successful restoration project? *

- Ecological improvements (e.g. Fish, aquatic flora, water quality etc)
- Hydromorphological improvements (e.g. quantity of water, dynamics of water flow, morphological conditions etc)
- Societal success (e.g. acceptance as improvement by societal groups, participation by societal groups, increased recreational activities etc)
- Economic success (e.g. works completed to time and budget, high benefit cost ratio etc)
- Post construction management and monitoring (e.g. after implementation, the site is managed and monitored to manage the restoration process)
- Sustainability of restoration (e.g. measures of improvement are sustained and / or continue to improve over a long period of time)
- Other

In your experience (covering all projects undertaken), what are the top 3 barriers to a successful restoration project? *

- Lack of funding
- National policy
- Local planning
- Long term versus short term planning
- Industry / business interests and / or objections
- Local community requirements and / or objections
- Other

Are you aware of / do you use, any ecosystem performance assessment frameworks? *

- REFORM – Restoring rivers for effective catchment management
- UN Framework for Freshwater Ecosystem Management
- Conceptual framework and practical structure for implementing ecosystem condition accounts
- Standards for Ecologically Successful River Restoration (Palmer et al, 2005)
- Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services (MAES)
- European Water Framework Directive (Qualitative scoring)
- International Principles and Standards for the Practice of Ecological Restoration (Gann et al, 2019)
- EUNIS habitat classification
- River Restoration Framework (Australia)
- Other

In your experience, when and how do you consider that a project has been successful? *

How do you measure this?

- Addressed/resolved a clear need
- Attracted multi-year funding for maintenance and is self-sustaining
- Inspired public participation
- Showed Scientific leadership
- Increased political will to address climate change
- Clear common goals that are achieved
- Other

We will be showcasing best practice examples of freshwater ecosystem restoration projects. Do you have examples of projects that you would like to share with others?

No

Privacy Settings

I confirm I have read and understood how we will use and manage your personal data in our [privacy policy](#)

I'm not a robot

[Privacy](#) [Terms](#)

[Save](#)

Appendix B: Main Survey – Personal Experience

HOME ABOUT CONSULTATION SHOWCASING PEOPLE HAPPENING IN FRESHWATER NEWS JOIN US LOG OUT

TEAM WORK AREA

Search Search

Main Survey – Personal Experience

Survey Event Details

You have successfully submitted this survey. Please only continue if you need to make changes

The EcoAdvance project is investigating factors that contribute towards the success of freshwater ecosystem restoration projects. Freshwater ecosystem restoration covered in this project are: lakes, rivers, perennial, intermittent, and ephemeral streams. Through this consultation we wish to look beneath the 'publicity' and understand what drives success and what may be barriers to success.

The following questions are aimed at collecting advice from you to help guide future restoration efforts and to make them more successful. Following the structured questions, which will be anonymized, please add any other recommendations. We will be in touch with you to follow up to showcase those efforts.

The survey is divided into 2 parts:

Part 1 asks for your judgement on Freshwater Ecosystem Restoration issues, based on your general knowledge and work experience.

Part 2 relates to specific project and personal experience.

Please complete any / all of the following survey screens; you can stop, save and recontinue at any point. You can submit your responses using the button on the final screen.

One of the EcoAdvance project outputs is the Prone2Success checklist. This is a list of key factors, that if considered, are likely to help improve a restoration project's chance of success. [You can see a preliminary work-in-progress draft here.](#)

Contact: EcoAdvance Team
Email: info@ecoadvance.eu

[Start the survey here »](#)

Consultation

[My Account](#)

[Consultation Platform](#)

✓ [Quick Survey](#)

✓ [Main Survey – Personal Experience](#)

✓ [Main Survey – Project Experience](#)

[Interview & Showcase Material](#)

[Log out](#)

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Main Survey – Personal Experience

Start of Survey 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

Metadata

Name

Mark

Morris

Type of Organisation you work for? *

Private company

Affiliation

SAMUI

Freshwater Ecosystem and restoration work that I am familiar with:
(Please add any links to projects, organisations, publications, etc.)

[Save for Later](#)

[Next »](#)

Main Survey – Personal Experience

Start of Survey 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

Overview of Success Factors

When considering freshwater ecosystem restoration, what factors, in your opinion, are important to making it successful?
 Allocate 0-1-2-3 ticks per box; more ticks = greater importance.
 Consider each of the factors listed below in relation to the different phases of a project.

Policy / legislation	Project Planning & Design	Financing the Project	Project Implementation	Post Construction Monitoring & Maintenance
The project is included in a River Basin Management Plan	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Water Framework Directive metrics on water quality demonstrate a need for action	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
The action meets local or national governance / policy objectives	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Approach	Project Planning & Design	Financing the Project	Project Implementation	Post Construction Monitoring & Maintenance
A plan for long term management of the scheme	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
A plan for monitoring performance of the scheme	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
The scale of the project (i.e. single point, local area, catchment etc)	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
A positive cost - benefit assessment	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Impacts	Project Planning & Design	Financing the Project	Project Implementation	Post Construction Monitoring & Maintenance
Impact on ecosystem services	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Impact on local agriculture	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Impact on water supply	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Impact on flood risk management	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Impact on biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Impact on carbon storage	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Impact on connectivity of the river / stream	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Participants	Project Planning & Design	Financing the Project	Project Implementation	Post Construction Monitoring & Maintenance
The involvement of scientists & a scientific basis for the action	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
The involvement of Industry	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
The involvement of Local Community	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
The involvement of an NGO	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Media / Publicity	Project Planning & Design	Financing the Project	Project Implementation	Post Construction Monitoring & Maintenance
A trigger or crisis event - environmental or political - helps support the action	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Media attention supports the action	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
Other - Add description below				
<input style="width: 100%; height: 100%;" type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			

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Main Survey – Personal Experience

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Topic 1: The impacts of Directives and policies on restoration success

Impact of the Water Framework Directive

Helps make projects prone to success by

- Setting defined water quality targets
- Requiring stakeholder collaboration
- Forcing long-term planning/budgeting
- Other

Improving these would make projects more prone to success?

- Enhanced funding and resources
- Clearer Stakeholder engagement requirements.
- Policy integration, coordination consolidation of planning and reporting with other Directives like Birds, Etc.
- Changing the 'one out all out rule'
- Stronger enforcement of environmental standards
- More flexibility for local governments to change
- Other

Any other comments on the WFD in relation to the restoration process?

Yes
 No

Other European policy initiatives

The Biodiversity 2030 strategy helps make restoration projects successful by:

- Drawing attention to Biodiversity loss
- Funding Biodiversity focused restoration projects
- Does not make a meaningful difference

The Restoration Law will strengthen our restoration process.

Yes
 No

Any other comments on the impacts of other policies (eg: Wastewater, Nitrate, Bird, Habitats)?

Yes
 No

My Country's National Policy

Our country's national policies help drive restoration success.

Yes
 No

We have a national strategy on the food-energy-water nexus that considers freshwater ecosystem restoration.

Yes
 No
 N/A

Local/regional Planning

The local planning process helps in implementing restoration projects.

Yes
 No

Local decisions balance the needs of restoration and the business impacts.

Yes
 No

Land availability has little influence on restoration projects.

Yes
 No

A clear mechanism for compensation where land is needed for restoration use makes projects prone to success.

Yes
 No

Key policy messages

What changes or additions would you recommend to the EC to make freshwater ecosystem restoration more successful?

What changes or additions would you recommend to your national government to make freshwater ecosystem restoration more successful?

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Main Survey – Personal Experience

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Topic 2: The impacts of funding on restoration success

Where do resources come from to fund freshwater ecosystem projects in your country?

- EU competitive project funding
- EU General funding
- National Government funding
- Local government funding
- Private donations
- Public-private partnerships
- Other

What does the availability of funding affect?

- Choice of project location
- Project methodology
- Project scope
- Project scale
- Project duration/timing
- Other

European funding support is critical for my projects?

- Yes
- No

Who makes project funding decisions? (check all that are relevant)

- National government agencies
- Regional or local authorities
- EU level
- Other

I have tried to obtain non-governmental sources of funding for restoration

- Yes and successful
- Yes but not successful
- No

In the future, what funding would make freshwater ecosystem restoration more prone to success?

- Local government investment
- Public-Private Partnerships
- EU investment
- Crowdfunding and community support
- User fees for use of restored freshwater sites
- Encouraging private businesses to build recreation facilities on public lands and manage them
- Better CAP payments to farmers to restore freshwater resources
- Other

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Main Survey – Personal Experience

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Topic 3: Community engagement

Community engagement is critical to restoration projects.

Yes
 No

It takes a crisis to get people involved

Yes
 No

Community participation from the very beginning is key to project success

Yes
 No

Pro-active community education about the need for restoration can make a big difference.

Yes
 No

If local communities benefit from restoration measures (improved ecosystem services...), I think they would offer a source of finance and / or support work.

Yes
 No

Local communities can support implementation of restoration projects.

Yes
 No

Add suggestions as to how Local Communities can best support implementation of restoration projects:

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Main Survey – Personal Experience

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Topic 4: Tools & Guidance

Is there relevant guidance available to stakeholders seeking to plan, finance and implement restoration projects?

Yes
 No

If yes – what do you use?
 If no – what is missing? What help are you seeking?

Does the availability of historic data impact freshwater ecosystem restoration chances for success?

Yes it is critical
 Yes helpful but not essential
 No

Solid scientific evidence that something has worked elsewhere is critical to freshwater ecosystem restoration

Yes
 No

Models that predict likely impacts and changes from freshwater restoration strategies make projects prone to success

Yes
 Maybe (if I knew how to use them)
 No
 I don't use models

I rely on official guidance manuals in instructions for freshwater ecosystem restoration

Yes, government manuals
 Yes government and NGO guidance
 Not much is relevant
 no

Which tools or methodologies support your project planning, implementation and monitoring?

- REFORM – Restoring rivers for effective catchment management
- UN Framework for Freshwater Ecosystem Management
- Conceptual framework and practical structure for implementing ecosystem condition accounts
- Standards for Ecologically Successful River Restoration (Palmer et al. 2005)
- Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services (MAES)
- European Water Framework Directive (Qualitative scoring)
- International Principles and Standards for the Practice of Ecological Restoration (Gann et al, 2019)
- EUNIS habitat classification
- River Restoration Framework (Australia)
- Other

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Appendix C: Main Survey – Project Experience

Main Survey – Project Experience

Start of Survey > 1

Specific Project Experience

Project(s)

Project Name	<input type="text"/>
Project Location	<input type="text"/>
Project Country	-- PLEASE SELECT --
Supporting Information For Example: website link; publication links; news articles etc.	<input type="text"/>

Project Experience:

Please provide details of your project experience via the table below. Consider each activity on the left against (i) whether this was considered in planning; (ii) how successful that aspect of the project was and (iii) how this contributed to the overall success of the project.

Please use the following scores for each item: 1: not at all, 2: moderately, 3: fully

If you prefer, just select those aspects which you felt significantly helped or hindered the project.

Project Design and Implementation	Considered in planning	Success rate	Contribution to impact
Clear goal setting	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Add Explanation (Optional)			
Project management	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Add Explanation (Optional)			
Long-term management of the scheme	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Add Explanation (Optional)			

Project funding	Considered in planning	Success rate	Contribution to impact
Detailed financial planning	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Add Explanation (Optional)			
Sufficient financing	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Add Explanation (Optional)			
Flexibility of budget	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Add Explanation (Optional)			
Efficient cost allocation/ cost utilisation	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Add Explanation (Optional)			
Timing of the budget availability	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Add Explanation (Optional)			

<i>Biophysical factors</i>	<i>Considered in planning</i>	<i>Success rate</i>	<i>Contribution to impact</i>
Choosing the right geographic scale Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Enhance connectivity of the waterbody Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Enhance ecological status of the waterbody Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Enhance naturalness of the landscape Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Enhance ecosystem services Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
<i>Legal and regulatory environment</i>	<i>Considered in planning</i>	<i>Success rate</i>	<i>Contribution to impact</i>
Requirements of EU directives Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Requirements of national laws Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Requirements of local regulations Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
<i>Societal embeddedness</i>	<i>Considered in planning</i>	<i>Success rate</i>	<i>Contribution to impact</i>
Coordination/cooperation with national administration Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Coordination/cooperation with local administration Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Communication and dissemination towards public Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Offering answer to local needs Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Contribution to the economic development/employment of the region Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Contribution to conflict resolution Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Improve stakeholders attitude and participation Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Improve cultural/historical/other values connected to the site of proposed restoration Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3

<i>Human resources</i>	<i>Considered in planning</i>	<i>Success rate</i>	<i>Contribution to impact</i>
Sufficient number of experts Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Involve experts with local knowledge and acceptance Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
<i>Assessment and monitoring</i>	<i>Considered in planning</i>	<i>Success rate</i>	<i>Contribution to impact</i>
Identifying and measuring baseline and success indicators Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3
Long-term monitoring of sustainability Add Explanation (Optional)	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3

Would you like to Add Details of Another Project

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Appendix D: Interview & Showcase Material

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Interview & Showcase Material

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Appendix E: Revised Survey for Project Period 2

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Advancing freshwater restoration

Survey

Select your survey language of preference (note: this survey is anonymous):

 Magyar

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- Survey (English)
- Enquête (Français)
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Factors Driving Successful Freshwater Restoration Projects

Factors Driving Successful Freshwater Restoration Projects

Please fill out this survey to help EcoAdvance identify what makes freshwater ecosystem restoration projects prone to success, or what barriers may impede success. Please answer as many of the questions as you can – it will take only 5-10 minutes!

mark.morris@samuifrance.com [Switch accounts](#)

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* Indicates required question

Where do you live? *

France

Which category fits you best? *

Engineers / Consultants / Practitioners

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Factors Driving Successful Freshwater Restoration Projects

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Topic 1: How important is community engagement in making a restoration project successful?

Restoration projects that are reactions to a crisis are more likely to be prone to success.

1 2 3 4 5

strongly disagree strongly agree

Community participation from the very beginning is key to project success.

1 2 3 4 5

strongly disagree strongly agree

Pro-active community education about the need for restoration can make a big difference in restoration success .

1 2 3 4 5

strongly disagree strongly agree

A transparent local planning process makes restoration projects prone to success.

1 2 3 4 5

strongly disagree strongly agree

Engaging stakeholders and understanding stakeholder conflicts can help resolve conflicts and make restoration more prone to success.

1 2 3 4 5

strongly disagree strongly agree

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Topic 2: How important are Tools & Guidance to making restoration projects successful?

The availability of historic data makes a difference to freshwater ecosystem restoration chances for success.

Yes, it is critical

Yes, it is helpful but not essential

No

Solid scientific evidence that something has worked elsewhere is critical to freshwater ecosystem restoration success.

Yes, it is critical

Yes, it is helpful but not essential

No

Models (or examples of good practices) that demonstrate likely impacts and changes from freshwater restoration strategies make projects prone to success.

Yes

Maybe (if I knew how to use them)

No

I don't use models

What methods or strategies do you think are most effective for implementing monitoring in a restoration project to ensure accurate assessment of implementation, progress and outcomes?

Your answer

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Topic 3: How important is an understanding and focus on improving ecosystem services to making projects more prone to success.

Restoration usually improves the ecological status and ecosystem functionality, and can also hold significant socio-economic value. Healthy ecosystems, rich in biodiversity, deliver more and multiple ecosystem services than ecosystems, which are degraded or exploited for maximizing the delivery of single or few services. How important is translated a project value and impact into ecosystem services terms?

Setting measurable goals in terms of ecosystem condition and improvements makes projects prone to success.

- Yes
- No

Using a reference condition makes a project more prone to success.

- No
- Yes

If yes, the best reference levels are made:

- by knowledge co-production with stakeholders (opinions, perceptions)
- by expert judgement
- by literature data of the site itself
- by literature data of similar site
- based on modelling
- Other: _____

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Setting goals in terms of specific ecosystem services make projects more prone to success.

- No
- Yes

If yes, which ones are most effective:

- supporting services (hydrological cycle, soil formation, nutrient cycle etc...)
- provisioning services (fish as food, improved quality of drinking water, agricultural crop)
- regulating services (flood mitigation, drought resistance, erosion control)
- cultural services (touristic attractiveness, aesthetic beauty)

Projects that prioritize between ecosystem functionality/ecological status and ecosystem services are more prone to success.

- No prioritizing is needed, they are in synergy
- Improvement of ecosystem services has priority even at the expense of better ecological status
- Improvement of ecological status has priority even at the expense of better ecosystem services
- Other: _____

Projects with restoration activities conducted over extended timeframes and across broad spatial scales are more likely to effectively enhance ecosystem services and ecological health compared to those with shorter-term, localized efforts.

- Yes
- No

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Topic 4: How important are regulations, policies and funding to restoration success.

Regulations and policies should serve as the foundational framework for restoration activities, delineating permissible activities such as land use changes, habitat restoration, and species reintroduction. Adequate funding should ensure that resources are available to carry out restoration projects and sustain them over time. We value your perspective on how important these aspects are and how they might be improved to make projects more prone to success.

The Water Framework Directive helps make projects prone to success by:

- setting defined water quality targets
- requiring stakeholder collaboration
- forcing long-term planning/budgeting
- Other: _____

The EU Biodiversity 2030 Strategy helps make projects prone to success by:

- requiring at least 10% of agricultural area under high-diversity landscape features
- requiring 30% of EU land surface to be protected
- requiring at least a third of PA (protected areas) to be strictly protected
- requiring a true Trans European Ecological Network to be established through the creation of ecological corridors
- requiring protected areas to be effectively managed
- Other: _____

The Restoration Law would make our restoration actions easier through a legal framework.

Yes

No

Don't know

Please explain

Your answer _____

Common Agricultural Policy would make restoration projects prone to success by:

- better payments to farmers to restore freshwater resources (legislation system for compensation payments)
- incentivizing sustainable agricultural practices (reduce pollution from agriculture)
- promoting ecological water recharge by ensuring that there are no charges for the use of river water in this context
- Other: _____

My country's national policies help make freshwater restoration projects prone to success.

Yes

No

Please explain

Your answer _____

Please tell us what kind of bureaucratic and legal obstacles make it difficult to initiate and implement a restoration project.

Please consider factors such as:

- Natura 2000 country reports set habitat type as not vulnerable
- contradictions in laws & regulations
- different sectoral priorities
- no correctly functioning helpdesk

Your answer _____

Key policy messages:

What changes or additions would you recommend to the European Commission to make freshwater ecosystem restoration more successful?

Your answer _____

What changes or additions would you recommend to your national or local government to make freshwater ecosystem restoration more successful?

Your answer _____

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In summary

In your opinion, what main factors make a freshwater restoration project more prone to success?

Your answer

In your opinion, what main factors are barriers to achieving a successful restoration project?

Your answer

Do you have any other comments or suggestions for the EcoAdvance team in our efforts to understand factors and drivers that make restoration projects more prone to success?

Your answer

Please list any relevant projects funded from European or other resources you are or have been involved in:

Your answer

This survey is anonymous. However, if you provide your name and email address below and check your interest, we will follow up.

Name

Your answer

Email

Your answer

Please Send survey results

I have a specific project that would make a good showcase for others to learn from

Please send me EcoAdvance news and event information

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